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Computing and Data Management for SABRE South

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Abstract

The SABRE (Sodium iodide with Active Background REjection) experiment aims to detect an annual rate modulation from dark matter interactions in ultra-high purity thallium-doped sodium-iodide (NaI(Tl)) crystals in order to provide a model independent test of the signal observed by DAMA/LIBRA. SABRE South is located at the Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory (SUPL), in regional Victoria, Australia.

SABRE South is designed to detect the signals generated by radiation and cosmic rays using both a 12kL liquid scintillator detector which will be contained in a steel vessel, and a plane of plastic scintillator modules located above the vessel to more reliably detect muons from cosmic-rays. In addition the crystal detector can host seven NaI(Tl) crystals to detect potential dark matter signals. As both the backgrounds from the outer detectors and potential signals from the crystal detectors are of interest the data taking strategy for SABRE South is to apply a minimal sustainable selection in DAQ to ensure no data of interest is lost. This is then followed by dedicated event building, a final software trigger step and further data reduction using the main SABRE South computing systems. SUPL is a newly constructed facility and as the first experiment, the SABRE computing infrastructure also needs to manage the data transfer to the main data centre in Melbourne serving as a template for future experiments. This proceeding will present details of the computing systems for SABRE South and how they will be used to support the experimental data taking and analysis.

1 Introduction

The SABRE experiment aims to search for an annual modulation arising from dark matter interactions in ultra-high purity NaI(Tl) crystals in order to provide a model-independent test of a signal observed by DAMA/LIBRA[1]. SABRE is a dual-site experiment located in the northern and southern hemispheres, with SABRE North located at Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso (LNGS) in Italy and SABRE South at the Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory (SUPL) in Australia. SABRE South anticipates generating to the order of 100 terabytes of raw and uncompressed physics data annually. Effectively managing this data is of high importance.

The recent opening of SUPL, 1024m underground at an active gold mine, brings numerous challenges for efficient data management and resource allocation for the SABRE South experiment. This conference proceeding addresses critical data management issues that need to be addressed with the opening of a new lab and outlines the computing systems for SABRE South that will be used to support the data acquisition and analysis. Challenges include balancing data processing and resources, developing computing and data management systems, and addressing bottlenecks in the system such as data acquisition rates, transfer speeds, and storage limitations. Balancing the use of computing resources in the lab is of particular interest as SABRE is the first experiment at SUPL and will be pioneering the technology used.

2 Striking a Balance

To strike an optimal balance between data processing and resource allocation, the SABRE South Collaboration will make use of powerful and widely available cloud-computing resources to minimise resources required in SUPL. With close proximity and strong affiliation to the University of Melbourne, SABRE South is able to leverage a range of cutting-edge resources available to researchers, including high-performance computing, cloud-based computing architecture, and robust storage capabilities. While we acknowledge the value of this connection and its potential advantages, the primary focus of our collaboration is on developing effective data processing strategies and robust systems capable of efficiently handling the substantial data generated at SUPL. We aim to streamline data transfer to Melbourne, where ample resources are available for further processing, analysis, and storage. This cloud-computing approach ensures that we can adapt to evolving environments and leverage additional enhancements offered by the University of Melbourne as part of our flexible system design. Please refer to Figure 1 for an illustration of the relationship between our available resources and possible data reduction methods.

Figure 1: Striking a balance: here, the orange represents what is possible in the DAQ, yellow is what SABRE South envisage for SUPL, and green is available through cloud-computing resources at Melbourne

3 Data Flow

When discussing data flow, our primary concerns encompass data acquisition, processing, both short-term and long-term storage, computing on the cloud, ensuring high availability, and implementing backup procedures. See figure 2 for the data flow diagram between SUPL and Melbourne.

SABRE SOUTH DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

Figure 2: Data Flow Diagram: depicting the main flow of data from the experiment and associated metadata. The dashed line indicates the divide between SUPL based systems and those at the University of Melbourne.

3.1 Data Acquisition

SABRE South is expected to generate $O(100 \text{ TB/y})$ of mostly unfiltered and uncompressed data, mainly composed of Photomultiplier Tube (PMT) waveforms and conditions metadata such as pressure, temperature, and other sensor readings. There are three main systems that acquire the experimental data; the NaI(Tl) crystal, liquid scintillator, and plastic scintillator systems. Additionally, there will be a stream of conditions data from various sensors. Between the main systems, there are six digitisers connected via optical links to three data acquisition (DAQ) computers, one for each of the main systems. Each digitiser can transfer up to 85 MB/s, leading to a limit of 510 MB/s[2]. SABRE South will aim to keep a sustained rate of 10% (51 MB/s) of this limit to allow for large spikes.

3.2 Initial Data Processing and Short-term Storage

For initial data processing and storage between the digitisers and DAQ computers at SUPL, SABRE South uses custom programs to store the acquired data locally and apply data reduction methods. These programs will employ elementary data reduction techniques, with a focus on threshold configuration, coincidence checking, zero suppression, and simple filtering. The anticipated outcome of the methods is a substantial reduction in annual data intake, from $O(100 \text{ TB/y})$ down to $O(20 \text{ TB/y})$.

SUPL will be linked to cloud computing services for data storage and processing in Melbourne via a 1 Gb/s optical link. In the case of connection failure, there is also a backup 4G connection. However, this 4G connection will not be used for experimental data transfer but for continued remote control and monitoring of SUPL based systems. As a consequence it is important to

have a sufficiently large storage buffer for the experiment in SUPL.

The DAQ computers at SUPL have a local storage capacity totalling 60 TB. This allocation of resources ensures the resilience of SABRE South computing systems in the face of potential disruptions to its connectivity with cloud computing infrastructure at Melbourne, providing a safeguarded operational buffer of up to three years.

3.3 Cloud Computing, Long-term Storage, and Backup

The SABRE South cloud computing services are centred around a highly available PostgreSQL[3] database management system, which serves as the core foundation for computing and data management for the experiment. In conjunction with the database, there will be a user interface (UI), high-performance computing (HPC), and task automation.

The database will store a wide range of metadata, including conditions, status, configuration, calibration, and other related experimental data. The experimental data from SUPL undergoes a final software trigger step and a more complex data reduction process than what is applied at SUPL, ensuring it is ready for long term storage. Once in long term storage, it becomes the primary experimental dataset and metadata for the datasets is also stored in the database.

The database for SABRE South will be configured for high availability to facilitate load balancing and query management. A highly available database is achieved by creating streaming replications of the database and if the master fails or is under too much load, connections and requests are redirected to another available copy of the database.

To provide a good user experience, end user access to the database is facilitated with a user interface. Various tools are employed to collectively form the interface for system monitoring and database query management, the most notable being:

- Prometheus[4]: collects and stores metrics from all systems as time series data
- Grafana[5]: enables you to query, visualize, alert on, and explore your metrics and logs
- Django[6]: a high-level Python web application framework that simplifies web application development

These tools integrate with each other and connect to and monitor both SUPL and cloud computing systems.

For analysis and simulation using the SABRE South experimental dataset, high-performance computing (HPC) is available through the cloud-computing service. HPC includes specialist high memory resources that are designed for processing large datasets and running multiple computing tasks simultaneously.

Task automation throughout the SABRE South computing systems will be managed using Apache Airflow[7]. Some examples of automation include transferring data from SUPL to Melbourne, inserting data into the PostgreSQL database, and backing up the database to an offsite location.

4 Conclusion

This conference proceeding has delved into managing the vast amount of data expected to be generated by the SABRE South Experiment at the Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory in Australia. The unfiltered and uncompressed data will primarily be composed of PMT waveforms and conditions metadata. Data reduction methods are expected to bring the initial size of O(100 TB/y) down to O(20 TB/y). There are many challenges in this endeavour, however, SABRE South's affiliation with the University of Melbourne, and its ability to leverage cutting-edge cloud-computing resources eliminates the need for extensive computing infrastructure at SUPL, allowing us to focus on developing efficient strategies and robust systems for data processing, compression, and seamless transfer to Melbourne. SABRE South's data acquisition, processing, storage, and backup procedures have been outlined. Furthermore, the crucial role of cloud-computing, long-term storage, and backup systems ensuring the integrity and availability of our data has been highlighted. With a strong emphasis on high availability and system automation, the foundation has been laid for a comprehensive and resilient data management infrastructure.

References

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